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Study of Total and Tribal Population Sex Ratio in Nandurbar District (Maharashtra, India)

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Abstract

This is an attempt to study the total and tribal population sex ratio of Nandurbar district. This paper reveals the tehsil-wise total and tribal population sex ratio in Nandurbar district. For this study using the 2011 census. The sex ratio denotes number of females per thousand males in a given population. Though it seems the simple male-female ratio, but it is an important indicator of the social development of a region. The higher value of the sex ratio indicates the good status of females in society as well as healthy practices and status of women in society. It's important to note that while the overall sex ratio among Scheduled Tribe communities in Nandurbar district is generally higher than the average, it's crucial to avoid overgeneralization and recognize the diverse realities within these communities. Factors influencing the sex ratio can vary among different tribes and geographical regions. Some tribes in the Nadurbar district have traditionally followed matriarchal structures, where descent and inheritance are traced through the mother's line. Unlike some other sections of society, many Scheduled Tribes don't practice the dowry system, which can lead to female infanticide or neglect in other communities. In the Study region high difference between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was observed in the low proportion of Scheduled Tribe population to total population.

Key Words: Sex ratio, Tribal Population, Nandurbar, Scheduled Tribe, and Disparity.

Introduction:

Tribal population is concentrated in geographically inaccessible areas so one can say the development of tribal, mostly depends on the distribution of population in relation to the resources available in the region (S. K. Pawar, K. C. Ramotra 2017), According to 2011 census, the population of Nandurbar district is 1648295 and the population density is 277 persons per sq. km. It has sex ratio favouring in males i.e. 978. The proportion of schedule tribe's population to the total tribal population of the districts is 69.28 percentages (1141933). The northern and southern tehsils namely Akkalkuwa, Dhadgaon (Akrani), and Nawapur have higher proportion of population. The minimum proportion of schedule tribe population found in Shahada and nandurbar tehsil.

Study Area:

Nandurbar district is located in North Maharashtra. The geographical location is 21°03' to 22°00' N latitude and 73°31' to 74°32' E longitude. The study region covered an area is 5034.30 sq. km. The population of Nandurbar district is 16, 48,295 (Census 2011). Among total population 83.29 percentage are rural and 17.71 percentage urban population. Nandurbar district form from formerly Dhule district on 1 July 1998.

Objectives:

- 1) To study tehsil-wise total and tribal population Sex Ratio in Nandurbar district.
- 2) To study tehsil-wise gap between total and tribal population Sex Ratio (2011-census) in Nandurbar district

Fig. No.1 Location Map

Database & Methodology:

The present study is mainly based on Secondary data, which is collected from the District Census Handbook, Census of Maharashtra and Statistical Abstract of Nandurbar district 2011 is selected for the present study. An attempt has been made to tabulate process, analyse and interpret the data by applying suitable statistical and cartographic techniques. For the total and tribal population sex ratio at tehsil and district level the simple sex ratio formula has been employed as follows: The sex ratio is calculated in terms of the number of females per thousand males.

It is calculated as under-
$$\text{Sex Ratio} = \frac{P_f}{P_m} * 1000$$

Pf = Number of females, Pm = Represents the number of males

Here studied total and tribal population sex ratio from 2011 census.

Total Population Sex Ratio of Nandurbar District (2011)

The sex ratio denotes number of females per thousand males in a given population. Though it seems the simple male-female ratio, but it is an important indicator of the social development of a region. According to the 2011 census, the total population of Nandurbar district is 1648295, out of which 833170 are male population and 815125 are female population. Total sex ratio of Nandurbar district is 978; this means that Nandurbar district has 978 females' population behind 1000 male population. On the tehsil level sex ratio varies from 926 to 1010 females per 1000 male population. The lowest total population sex ratio was observed in Akkalkuva tehsil with 926 females per 1000 male population because of being more proportion of the non-tribal population in Akkalkuva town and surrounding villages which has no gender inequality. While highest total population sex ratio noted in Navapur tehsil is 1010 females per 1000 male population because of a high proportion of the Scheduled tribe population which has gender equality and a high literacy rate. Followed by Navapur tehsil, Taloda, Dhadgaon, and Shahada tehsils also have higher sex ratios than the average sex ratio of Nandurbar district respectively 1010, 999, and 980 females per 1000 male population.

Table No.1: Nandurbar District: Total Population Sex Ratio in 2011

Sr. No.	Name of Tehsil	Male Population	Female Population	Sex Ratio (Per 000' Male Population)
1	Navapur	135254	136598	1010
2	Nandurbar	129260	127149	968
3	Taloda	66493	66798	1001
4	Akkalkuva	127633	118228	926
5	Dhadgaon	97902	97852	999
6	Shahada	174499	171853	980
Nandurbar District		833170	815125	978

Source: District census handbook Nandurbar, 2011

Fig. No. 2 – Map-Total Sex Ratio of Nandurbar District in 2011

Sex Ratio of Scheduled Tribe Population

The sex ratio is the most important component of the demography of any region. The proportion of the scheduled tribe’s population to the total tribal population of the Nandurbar districts is 69.28 percent (1141933). The majority of the population belongs to tribal communities.

Table No.2: Nandurbar District: Scheduled Tribe Population Sex Ratio in 2011

Sr. No.	Name of Tehsils	Scheduled Tribe Population in 2011			ST Sex Ratio (Per 000' Male Population)
		Total	Males	Females	
1	Navapur	232501	114968	117533	1022
2	Nandurbar	167431	83095	84336	1015
3	Taloda	123634	61240	62394	1019
4	Akkalkuwa	209586	104973	104613	997
5	Dhadgaon	187806	93842	93964	1001
6	Shahada	220975	109908	111067	1011
Nandurbar District		1141933	568026	573907	1010

Source: District census handbook Nandurbar, 2011

Fig. No. 3 Map-Scheduled Tribe Population Sex Ratio Nandurbar District in 2011

Table 2 reveals the Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio in 2011. In the Nandurbar district Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was observed by 1010 females per 1000 male Scheduled Tribe population. The highest Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was noted in Navapur tehsil with 1022 females per 1000 male Scheduled Tribe population because of high literacy and gender equality. Followed by Navapur tehsil, Taloda, Nandurbar, and Shahada tehsils also had a higher sex ratio than the total sex ratio of the Scheduled Tribe population in 2011.

It's important to note that while the overall sex ratio among Scheduled Tribe communities in Nandurbar district is generally higher than the average, it's crucial to avoid overgeneralization and recognize the diverse realities within these communities. Factors influencing the sex ratio can vary among different tribes and geographical regions.

Some tribes in the Nadurbar district have traditionally followed matriarchal structures, where descent and inheritance are traced through the mother's line. Unlike some other sections of society, many Scheduled Tribes don't practice the dowry system, which can lead to female infanticide or neglect in other communities.

Many tribal communities have strong connections to nature and revere mother goddesses. This deep-rooted respect for the feminine principle could contribute to valuing girls and women. Certain tribes have traditional community councils or panchayats with regulations against female infanticide or other harmful practices. These all-socio-cultural factors are responsible for the high sex ratio in the Scheduled Tribe population.

Gap between Total and Scheduled Tribe Population Sex Ratio

Table No. 3: Nandurbar District: Gap Between Total and Scheduled Tribe Sex Ratio (2011)

Sr. No	Tehsils	Sex Ratio (No. of Females per 000' Male Population) in 2011		Gap Between Total and Scheduled Tribe Population Sex Ratio
		Total	Scheduled Tribe	
1	Navapur	1010	1022	12
2	Nandurbar	968	1015	47
3	Taloda	1001	1019	18
4	Akkalkuwa	926	997	71
5	Dhadgaon	999	1001	2
6	Shahada	980	1011	31
Nandurbar District		978	1010	32

Source: District census handbook Nandurbar, 2011 and tabulated by Researcher.

Fig. No.4 - Gap between Total and Scheduled Tribe Population

Table No. 3 and Figure No. 4 reveal the variance between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio in the Nandurbar district. All tehsils of Nandurbar district have observed more sex ratio among the Scheduled Tribe community than the total population. In the Nandurbar district, the overall difference between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was observed by 32, which means the total population sex ratio was 978 while the Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was 1010 females per thousand male population in 2011. The highest positive gap between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio has been noted in Akkalkuwa tehsil by 71 because of their high proportion of non-tribal population in Akkalkuwa town which has a comparatively low sex ratio. Followed by Akkalkuwa tehsil, Nandurbar tehsil has also a high difference between total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio with 47 due to Nandurbar town which has more male population as immigrants for employment. The lowest disparity between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio has been observed in Dhadgaon tehsil by only 2 because the majority of the Scheduled Tribe population. In the Study region high difference between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was observed in the low proportion of Scheduled Tribe population to total population.

Conclusion:

The lowest total population sex ratio was observed in Akkalkuwa tehsil with 926 females per 1000 male population because of being more proportion of the non-tribal population in Akkalkuwa town and surrounding villages which has no gender inequality. While highest total population sex ratio noted in Navapur tehsil is 1010 females per 1000 male population because of a high proportion of the Scheduled tribe population which has gender equality and a high literacy rate. The highest Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was noted in Navapur tehsil with 1022 females per 1000 male Scheduled Tribe population because of high literacy and gender equality. Followed by Navapur tehsil, Taloda, Nandurbar, and Shahada tehsils also had a higher sex ratio than the total sex ratio of the Scheduled Tribe population in 2011. The highest gap between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio has been noted in Akkalkuwa tehsil by 71 because of their high proportion of non-tribal population in Akkalkuwa town which has a comparatively low sex ratio. The lowest disparity between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio has been observed in Dhadgaon tehsil by only 2 because the majority of the Scheduled Tribe population. In the Study region high difference between the total and Scheduled Tribe population sex ratio was observed in the low proportion of Scheduled Tribe population to total population.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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